

D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3
Report on the probes
designed to targets
developed in WP3 for C.
parvum and G. duodenalis

Workpackage 4 of
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE

Responsible Partners: P27-ISS, P41-SVA, P-30 RIVM

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D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3

REPORT ON THE PROBES DESIGNED TO TARGETS DEVELOPED IN WP3 FOR *C. PARVUM* AND *G. DUODENALIS*

BACKGROUND

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – *PARASite* Detection, *ISolation* and *Evaluation*

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>);

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE –WP4 Parasite enrichment strategies;

Task:

JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP4-T2 Development of post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies.

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PARADISE aims to increase the understanding of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* genomics and through that knowledge design novel multi-locus typing schemes (MLST) with improved resolution. To be able to use the novel MLST, PARADISE will develop and test novel enrichment strategies to overcome the limitations of current technologies, including pre-DNA extraction enrichment, approaches and a post-DNA extraction enrichment.

PARADISE WP4 aims to improve the performance of current approaches to detect *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* (oo)cyst contamination in food through the development of parasite enrichment strategies, which should improve the sensitivity of detection and deliver cost effective methods applicable to food matrices.

Objectives of PARADISE WP4 are:

- ✓ To develop two pre-DNA extraction protocols based on two alternative affinity reagents, nanobodies (single-chain variable fragment antibodies) and aptamers (oligonucleotides that bind to specific target molecules);
- ✓ To assess nanobodies and aptamers application for magnetic capture of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in different matrices;
- ✓ To develop a protocol for post-DNA extraction enrichment to concentrate parasite DNA based on hybridization of target-specific biotinylated probes.
- ✓ To evaluate pre- and post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies by inter-laboratory comparison

This deliverable reports on the third objective of PARADISE WP4, design and testing of hybridization biotinylated, single-stranded DNA probes specific to pull-out DNA of *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* from complex DNA solutions.

Figure 1. Illustration of WP4. D) is task WP4-T2, post-DNA extraction enrichment of specific markers. Figure is adopted from PARADISE proposal

WP4-T2. Description of work

The objective of this task is the development and evaluation of a protocol for post-DNA extraction enrichment based on sequence-based capture of low abundance target DNA in matrices such as faeces, water (drinking, recreational and wastewater as well as washing water from fresh produce) and archived DNA from suspected foodborne outbreaks.

In Y4, WP4-T2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first annual period of the project, towards the establishment of hybridization probe magnetic capture procedures for enrichment of DNA sequences of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in different matrices (i.e. feces, different types of water, and archived DNA material). SVA and RIVM will test and optimize the magnetic procedure system as soon as appropriate probes will be available. For this purpose, individual or mixed *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* DNA at different concentrations will be used to spike different matrices. Although a standard molecular test is not available for *Cryptosporidium* or *Giardia*, the sensitivity of detection between enriched and non-enriched samples will be compared based on qPCR protocols established at VRI. In the case of *Cryptosporidium*, the qPCR guideline experimentally defined by the EFSA funded project IMPACT will also be considered. A protocol will be prepared and further used by inter-laboratory comparison.

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The work reported here is highly dependent on tasks within WP2 and WP3 (Figure 2). In Milestone “M-JRP-PARADISE-22¹ Hybridization probes tested for robustness and sensitivity available”, we reported on the development and optimization of systems for the commonly used markers for genotyping in *C. parvum* and *Giardia*.

The continuation of this task within WP4 is aimed at designing similar systems for the markers chosen in WP3. We have identified several suitable markers, as reported in “D-JRP PARADISE-WP3.2 Report on the identification of MLST markers for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*”². However, the number of markers is still very high for both organisms and a further selection is needed before implementation of the MLST.

Figure 2. Structure of Paradise WPs and how information for WP4 is generated through WP 2 and 3.

Probe design – plan and experience gained within WP4-T2

Once the final sets of markers for *C. parvum* and *Giardia* have been selected, probe design can take place. Probe(s) are designed for each marker but will be used simultaneously in the hybridization capture (see Figure 3).

A probe set for each marker can be either just one probe or several depending on the actual sequence of the marker and flanking regions. Usually one hybridization probe for each strand is designed³. This enables exponential amplification from first PCR cycle. However, in many systems one probe has much better affinity and there is no need to optimize probes for both strands. If this is the case, one will have to consider that the first PCR cycle is used to create second strand target before exponential amplification can start.

Ideally, probes are designed to hybridize just outside the fragment to be amplified. However, this is not always possible (e.g. in case this is a non-conserved region) and there are systems with high sensitivity also when the probe hybridizes inside the amplified region. One example is the SSU hybridization probe system created in PARADISE. The closer the probe is to the target the more likely it is the system has high sensitivity.

The affinity of the probes are determined by the melting temperature (T_m) (e.g. secondary structure of the target molecule, etc.). To ensure a T_m to be high enough (likely ranging between 60 and 80 degrees Celsius) several parameters can be adjusted. For instance, a GC-poor capture probe can be designed to be longer, or LNAs (Locked Nucleic Acids, a class of bicyclic RNA analogues with an exceptionally high affinity for their complementary DNA and RNA target molecules) can be incorporated⁴. If there is variation among sequences, longer probes are more likely to also capture variants. There is also the possibility to incorporate degenerated bases in the probe to achieve perfect basepairing also for variants.

Helper probes may be an option as they may enhance the yield. One example where helper probes have been extensively evaluated is in the *gp60* hybridization probe system designed within PARADISE. Table 1 below illustrates one hybridization probe system where helper probes have been evaluated.

Table 1. Results showing effect of addition of different amounts of helper probe.

	Sample 1 (Cq)	Sample 2 (Cq)	Sample 3 (Cq)
No Helper probes	37.94	39.03	37.80
1X Helper probe	36.24	37.36	39.26
8X Helper probe	36.29	-	37.86
40X Helper probe	34.84	36.85	36.18

Protocol optimization

Once the probe systems have been designed a protocol needs to be optimized. During year 3 in WP4 we have worked through the protocol and have optimized parameters, both for a marker in *Giardia* and for two markers in *C. parvum*. An illustration of a general workflow is provided in Figure 3.

Parameters that can be optimized:

- Time and temperatures. These may vary within every system and depending on what matrix the original sample is from.
- Amounts of biotinylated probes and magnetic beads and more importantly, the ratio between these two, can be optimized.
- Fragmentation of the DNA may be done before addition of capture probes. This is accomplished by restriction enzymes, bead beating or sonication and aims to make the genomic DNA more accessible for the probes. In the case of PARADISE samples we develop the protocol for already extracted DNA and it is likely already fragmented following the DNA extraction.

NEXT STEPS

As the work to design probes and to develop a protocol for the system is dependent on the markers finally included we have not finalized this process. A detailed plan is in place, and based on the experience in developing the three earlier systems within PARADISE, we are confident this will be a fast process once the final marker sets are selected.

Figure 3. Workflow of specific DNA fishing.

References

1. M-JRP-PARADISE-22 Hybridization probes tested for robustness and sensitivity available
2. D-JRP-PARADISEWP3.2 Report on the identification of MLST markers for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (<https://zenodo.org/record/5494476#.YTieyxmSmUk>)
3. Forensic Science International: Genetics 29 (2017) 61–70.
4. Nucleic Acids Research, 2004, Vol. 32, No. 7 e64 DOI:10.1093/nar/gnh056